

AN OVERVIEW OF THE PUBLIC HEALTH DATA CONSTRAINTS IN INDIA AND A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

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Abstract

The paper aims to put forward the various constraints of the existing public health data and health indicators in the country. The paper further aims to make the public health data/ health indicators realistic and making an end of the existing data morphs, dwarfs, and data, chauvinism persisted in the health sector. The paper ultimately came out with a conceptual framework. The proposed framework would make a required demarcation in the existing public health data and health indicators. It would be possible to make a demarcation in terms of the respective contributions of the public and private health sectors and in terms of the respective social groups such as income, age, gender, SC/ST/OBS/General etc. The health needs of different social groups are different and it was required to have information about the health status of different social groups for proper public health planning, policy, and programs.

Key words: Public Health Data; Health Indicators; Health Data Constraints in India; Health Statistics; Health Information Management System (HMIS).

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INTRODUCTION

The public health data in India can be described as an amalgamation of health related demographic data, health indicators, health determinants and various morbidity, mortality reported by health centres, practitioners, and institutions. There are several governmental and nongovernmental data sources of people's health in India. Such sources may include, however, not limited to "Sample Registration System" (RGI, 2012), "National Family Health Survey (NFHS)" (IIPS, 2012), "District Level Household and Facility Survey (DLHS)", "Rural Health Survey" (MOHFW, 2012), "Multi Indicator Survey" by Unicef (UNICEF, 2010) and "Times Series Data" (Rob Hyndman, 2012). In addition, "Country's Health Statistics" maintained by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2012) and also by the "Central Intelligence Agency" of USA (CIA, 2012). However, most of previously mentioned data sources use the sample survey to present those data. Several studies have found those data very irrelevant for a perfect public health planning, policy, and programming (PHPP).

The health data management is unique and has its own operating environment and sets of technical requirements. As a result, the execution of National Health Mission various constraints emerged, which required to be affirmed, addressed at the earliest. The data moves upward from health field workers. The progression of data from field operations may invariably have significant negative impact on overall health data management. By definition, a data constraint refers to any condition, such as temporal/spatial limitations and safety/quality concerns, which may prevent appropriate data management. A successful health policy, planning, program, its execution and control rely on effective identification and management of data management constraints. It is required to keep a global overview of health data management and integrating the same in a most localized data management framework.

The quality data have many features such as Access Security, Accessibility, Accuracy and Appropriateness; Reputation, Reliable, Realtime, and Relevance; Complete and Concise; Understandable and Interpretable; Objectivity, Representativeness, and Value (Unite For Sight, 2019). The quality of data is critical to assessing the National Burden of Disease (NBD) and developing health initiatives. We live in an era of unprecedented technological advancement, which has provided us with increased access to data. However, just because data have become more available does not mean that all data is accurate and reliable (Unite For Sight, 2019). Accurate, timely and accessible health care data plays a vital role in the planning, development and maintenance of health care services. Quality improvement and the timely dissemination of quality data are essential if health authorities

wish to maintain health care at an optimal level (WHO, 2003). Reliable and accurate health information is essential for monitoring health and for evaluating and improving the delivery of health care services and programs (Mphatswe, et al., 2011). Data quality refers to the condition of a set of values of qualitative or quantitative variables. There are many definitions of data quality, but data are generally considered high quality if it is "fit for [its] intended uses in operations, decision making and planning" (Thomas, 2013) (Fadahunsi, et al., 2019). For several years now, leaders from United Nations agencies and global health partnerships have been making increasingly loud calls for more and better health data (Boerma, 2015). The quality of healthcare data affects every decision made along the patient care range. The demand for accurate and reliable data has never been more important. The sharing of healthcare data is far reaching. Providers such as physician groups, hospitals, skilled nursing facilities and pharmacies create healthcare data at the source during the normal course of business. Then the data transformed into secondary data and shared with entities like payers, clearinghouses, third party vendors, health agencies, government agencies, health information organizations, and the consumer. Each entity may have different purposes for collecting and using the data. The focus could range from the clinical, administrative, or financial aspects of data.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

I came across numerous instances when such data failed to apply and justify on the grounds. The overall Indian society consisted of numerous social groups because of diversified ethnicity, geography, income, age, gender, and traits. If there would be such a huge diversity in the population, the public health data cannot be uniform. The existing aggregated public health data is neither a data of mine, yours, or anyone else. This aggregation of the public health data could never be beyond doubts and seriously questioned by numerous development practitioners and experts.

A substantial amount of studies, opinions by various experts indicated that a range of health and demography related data in this country are deficient due to one reason or another. The deficiency may be because of the methods, scope, and transparency in data collection, analysis, and presentation.

Therefore, there is apparently a major problem of demarcation in the existing Health Information Management System (HIMS) of the country. The existing system does not demarcate between the respective contributions of the public and private health sectors; moreover, there is no demarcation in terms of the respective social groups such as caste, category, gender, religion, and age. The sampled

and statistical data by various governmental and nongovernmental agencies is also not real time.

Reliable and valid data collection are key to the development of any country. A data cannot be just for the sake of having a data. Frequent laments in policy corridors are "we do not collect this data," "we are not sure whether these data are available," "these data are not reliable," or "these data are not valid." Decisions in such scenarios are *ad hoc* and/or based on the best judgment or the limited data that are available for decision-making. In such a scenario, cross-sectional survey data offer a panacea and are frequently referred and cited while making policy decisions (Zodpey & Negandhi, 2016).

Although, the National Statistical Commission (NSC) does not collect direct data for the health sector. However, it has remained a source for various data sets used in health policy and planning. The NSC was in deep trouble after the resignations of its key functionaries over data transparency issues (Chowdhury, 2019). This incident is an indicative of the fact that there were some basic and conceptual deficiencies in data retrieving in this country.

While a range of health and health care entities collect data, the data do not flow among these entities in a cohesive or standardized way. Until data gets integrated across entities, some redundancy will remain.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The World Health Organization (WHO) in a study has found that the reliable nationwide population-based data on major non-communicable diseases, such as ischemic heart disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, stroke, low-back and neck pain and depression are scanty in India, as are similar data on injuries. Such data are also unavailable for tuberculosis and pneumonia (Dandona, Pandey, & Dandona, 2016). Information on "race" and "ethnicity" is routinely collected in medical settings and used in research (Moscou, Anderson, Kaplan, & Valencia, 2003). A study concluded that there is a lack of reliable health data and poor management of district health information systems in low and middle-income countries (LMIC). Despite poor practices, improved health care service delivery with improved health data efficiency may be possible (Ndabarora, Chipps, & Uys, 2014). In the future, data quality assessment of health needs to consider equally the three dimensions of data quality, data, data use and data process (Chen, Hailey, Wang, & Yu, 2014). Small-scale local data resources may serve to provide a highly resolved estimate of health effects, which can be spatially heterogeneous in highly populated urban centers in developing countries (Nori-Sarma, et al., 2017). According to the Australian Health Department, CDC guidelines data quality "reflects the completeness and validity of the data recorded in the health surveillance system" (Commonwealth of Australia, 2011).

According to C.K. Mishra, former health secretary of India, the data from the latest round of the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) — the major source for detailed health statistics in India, conducted under the aegis of the ministry of health and family welfare (MoHFW) itself — is unreliable for certain states (Bansal, 2017). In a study it was found that while the National Rural Health Mission and National Urban Health Mission (NUHM) have resulted in important improvements to India's health system, there remain key data gaps that need to fill, and approaches that need 'fine tuning' (Tandon, 2018). The credibility of India's data systems is under serious threat with the recent controversy over the employment data of the National Sample Survey. While the Census of India and the National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO) have a good reputation, when it comes to data related to the social sector — health, education, nutrition — the situation, even with these sources (along with other large data sets), has been deficient on numerous counts (Bhatty & Sinha, 2019). For some time now, health planners in India have been seeking better availability of disease burden data and trends at subnational levels. These are necessary for informed health policy and programming at the state and district levels, a prerequisite to improve population

health based on local trends (ICMR; IHME, 2017). In a study it was found that, to facilitate the transition of HIS in India from its present state to a level where it is compliant with international standards, there is a need to review the information processes and existing systems; Highlighted the existing flaws in the system and suggested ways to improve upon them (Tripathi, Sharma, & Nagarajan, 2018).

The studies reviewed indicated that there is a need for improvement in various health related data. It is needed to make those data substantial, real, and real time. The literature review shows that past studies are primarily focused on understanding and modeling a particular type of constraint, such as data need, transparency in data collection, and problems of Health Information Management Systems (HMIS). There was a lack of specific literature suggesting an India specific health data collection and presentation. India is a diversified country having many languages and cultures. There are different health needs of different social groups and hence a unified approach would not be suitable. The diversity in approach was required in addressing the diverse needs.

METHODS

The primary research method for this study was a literature review along with the conceptual framework. In addition, the constraint identification and classification through a structured approach was also the very first step. There was review of various types of constraints in health data retrieving and presentation. Based on this understanding, a classification method developed to categorize constraint factors for the purpose of constraint identification and modeling.

In the second stage of this study, existing constraint modeling methods identified based on a comprehensive review of current practices and academic researches. Finally, once the constraint classification and modeling techniques identified, a conceptual framework for total constraint management outlined.

A dedicated framework of methods used for various research components identified and scheduled. We defined the success parameters taking into account the diverse goals of the study. A survey instrument was applied to a significant population survey of 2 selected villages.

The survey instrument designed to gather information on various demographic and health related data from the entire population. A series of questions for use in conducting case studies of various data sources and health institutions conducted. The case studies focused the data process, accessibility, cost, reliability, and validity with real time aspects. A group of leading data experts, data engineers, surveyors, and data managers were engaged in data collection, evaluation, and analysis.

OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this article has been to highlight various constraints in the public health data from India and to suggest a conceptual framework.

FINDINGS

Different social groups in India having different health needs and there was the unavailability of respective data about respective social groups at different levels. Even we should know their specific DNA profile because a particular disease in a particular social group cannot be addressed in a uniform manner.

The periodical reports submitted by various public health functionaries and institutions were not reliable in many parts of India. Such data cannot be aggregated and presented through a common Health Information Management Systems (HMIS) at the district, state, and central levels.

There was no account of private health expenditure in India and as private health, institutions and practitioners were not part of the mandatory reporting system.

There was no uniform National Patient Registry System in India. Registries, insurance companies, and third-party payers would be more than ever, closely examining a health program outcome.

The Micro Health Indicators and other Health Data in this country cannot be demarcated in terms of different social groups such as Caste, Category, Religion, Gender, Geographic Locations, Age, and Occupation. In addition, not all those data maintained for the respective villages, punchayats, districts, and sub district levels. It was adversely affecting proper public health policy, planning, and programming.

The data were not real time as most data were periodical in the manner being published with a time gap of 6 months to 3-4 years.

CONCLUSION

However, it was possible to present a realistic and real time data for this country at various levels, however, public health functionaries were ignored over the issues and failed to apply minds the manner a reliable and valid data can be generated and distributed.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The existing system of data collection would be required to undergo a change. The vital or mandatory registration cannot be limited to mere recording birth and deaths; however, it must include morbidity also.

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APPENDIX 1

Health Indicators and Formula Thereon used for Various Health Indicators

S. No.	Health Indicator	Formula		
1.	Birth (crude) rate	=	(number of births) + (total population)	X 1,000
2.	Age-specific birth rate	=	(number of live births to females in a specific age group) + (female population in that age group)	X 1,000
3.	Teen-age birth rate	=	(number of births to females aged 10-19) + (female population aged 10-19)	X 1,000
4.	Abortion rate	=	(number of abortions) + (female population aged 15-44)	X 1,000
5.	Teenage abortion rate	=	(number of abortions to females aged 10-19) + (female population aged 10-19)	X 1,000
6.	Estimated total fetal losses	=	20 percent of births + 10 percent of abortions	
7.	Estimated pregnancies	=	number of births + number of abortions + estimated total fetal losses	
8.	Pregnancy rate	=	(number of births + number of abortions+ estimated total fetal losses) + (female population 15-44 years of age)	X 1,000
9.	Teenage pregnancy rate	=	(number of births to females aged 10-19 + number of abortions to females aged 10-19 + estimated total fetal losses to females aged 10-19) + (female population 10-19 years of age)	X 1,000

10.	Total fertility rate	=	(five-year age-specific birth rates for \sum females aged 10 to 49)	X 5
11.	Percent low weight births	=	(number of births with a birth weight less than 2500 grams) + (number of births)	X 100
12.	Infant mortality rate	=	(number of deaths to live born infants under one year of age) + (number of births)	X 1,000
13.	Neonatal mortality rate	=	(number of deaths to live born infants occurring within the first 27 days of life) + (number of births)	X 1,000
14.	Postneonatal mortality rate	=	(number of deaths to live born infants occurring after the first 27 days of life but before one year of age) + (number of births)	X 1,000
15.	Death (crude) rate	=	(number of deaths) + (total population)	X 1,000
16.	Cause-specific death rate	=	(number of deaths for a specific cause) + (total population)	X 100,000
17.	Age-specific death rate	=	(number of deaths for a specific age group) + (population for that age group)	X 1,000
18.	Marriage rate	=	(number of marriages) + (total population)	X 1,000
	Divorce (dissolution) rate	=	(number of divorces and annulments) + (total population)	X 1,000
